

E-ISSN:3043-6028

VOLUME 4: NUMBER 2; MARCH, 2026

**A COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF COUNT REGRESSION MODELS
FOR CANCER MORTALITY USING AGGREGATED DATA: A
RETROSPECTIVE STUDY OF CANCER PATIENTS IN ONCOLOGY
DEPARTMENT, BSUTH, MAKURDI**

Michael Kudyo Adamu, Victoria I. Adamu, James S. Ivande, and Geoffery I. Zaaya
Department of Statistics,
Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi
Benue State Nigeria

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

MICHAEL KUDYO ADAMU
Department of Statistics,
Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi
Benue State, Nigeria
Email: adamu.michael@uam.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Cancer death data are commonly analysed using count regression models; however, the equidispersion assumption of the Poisson model is often violated in aggregated surveillance data. Failure to account for overdispersion can lead to biased inference and misleading conclusions. This study aimed to comparatively evaluate Poisson and Negative Binomial count regression models for modeling cancer death using aggregated data and to identify the most appropriate specification for reliable inference. Aggregated annual data on cancer cases and deaths from 2010 to 2022 covering five cancer types were analysed. Death counts were modelled using Poisson regression, classical Negative Binomial (NB2), and modified Negative Binomial (NB1) models. An offset for the logarithm of total cancer cases was included to account for exposure and enable rate-based interpretation. The model adequacy and distributional properties were accessed using the exploratory data analysis (EDA) and graphical diagnostics. The log-likelihood, AIC and BIC were used to compare the model performance. The incidence rate ratios (IRRs) were used to report the results with 95% C.I. It was revealed by the EDA, a substantial variability and overdispersion in the cancer death counts, clearly the variance exceeded the mean. Comparatively, the poisson regression model showed a poor fit, while both Negative Binomial model and the modified negative binomial model showed significant improvements. The Modified Negative Binomial (NB1) model performed best when compared

to all competing models with the smallest AIC and BIC values. The negative binomial models are clearly preferable to the Poisson model with aggregate cancer mortality data. The modified negative binomial (NB1) model fitted the best and should be preferred to model the over-dispersed cancer death counts. These results point to the need for proper model choice in analyzing pooled health outcome data.

KEYWORDS: Count regression, Poisson model, Negative binomial model, AIC, BIC, Overdispersion, Aggregated data.

INTRODUCTION

In the world today, cancer remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality, imposing a significant burden on health systems and the society. In spite of the advances in the prevention, early detection, and treatment, cancer-related deaths continue to rise in many low- and middle-income countries, most likely due to presenting late cases, limited access to care, and the constraints on the health system (Bray et al., 2018; Sung et al., 2021). It is thus vital to know the patterns of cancer mortality in order to plan appropriate interventions, allocate resources, and monitor progress toward controlling cancer. Aggregate cancer-mortality counts at a population level are frequently reported which may be summarized by year, area, or disease site. These types of data structures naturally lead to the consideration of count regression models since they are suitable for responses in non-negative integer forms (Cameron and Trivedi 2013). Among them, the Poisson regression model is the most widely used due to its mathematical simplicity and interpretability. But the Poisson model is based on a stringent assumption of equidispersion under which the mean and variance of the response variable are equal. In practice, cancer death data often violate this assumption because of unobserved heterogeneity, clustering, and temporal variation, leading to overdispersion (Hilbe, 2011). When overdispersion is present, Poisson regression tends to underestimate standard errors, inflating the statistical significance of covariates and potentially leading to incorrect inferences (Gardner et al., 1995).

To address this limitation, the Negative Binomial (NB) regression model has been widely adopted as a more flexible alternative. The Negative Binomial model introduces an additional dispersion parameter that allows the variance to exceed the mean, making it particularly suitable for overdispersed count data (Lawless, 1987; Hilbe, 2011). Several variants of the Negative Binomial model exist, differing primarily in how the variance is modelled as a function of the mean. The most commonly used form, often referred to as NB2, assumes a quadratic mean–variance relationship. An alternative specification, known as NB1 or the modified Negative Binomial model, assumes a linear mean–variance relationship and may be more appropriate when overdispersion increases proportionally with the mean rather than quadratically (Cameron & Trivedi, 2013; Winkelmann, 2008). Despite its theoretical relevance, the NB1 model has received comparatively limited attention in applied public health research, particularly in cancer death studies.

In the context of aggregated cancer data, additional methodological considerations arise. Death counts are strongly influenced by the size of the population at risk or the number of diagnosed cases. Failure to account for this exposure can obscure true differences in death risk. Incorporating an offset term, such as the logarithm of total cancer cases, allows regression coefficients to be interpreted as effects on death rates rather than raw counts, improving comparability across cancer types and time periods (Frome, 1983). Although numerous studies have applied Poisson or Negative Binomial regression to cancer incidence and death data, relatively few have conducted a systematic comparison of alternative count regression specifications using aggregated cancer death data. Moreover, empirical evidence guiding the choice between different Negative Binomial variance structures remains sparse. Given the growing reliance on routinely collected aggregated data for public health decision-making, rigorous evaluation of appropriate statistical models is essential.

- ***Aim and Objectives***

This study aimed to conduct a comparative evaluation of count regression models for modeling cancer death using aggregated data, with a view to achieving the following objectives:

1. To examine the distributional properties and dispersion effects of aggregated cancer death counts.
2. To fit Poisson, classical Negative Binomial (NB2), and modified Negative Binomial (NB1) regression models with appropriate exposure offsets.
3. To compare the performance of the models based on likelihood criteria.
4. To choose the best model for making credible inference on cancer aggregated data.

• **Statement of the Problem**

Cancer death data are commonly analysed as aggregated counts, yet many studies rely on Poisson regression without adequately assessing its underlying equidispersion assumption. In reality, the aggregated number of cancer deaths tends to be highly overdispersed due to unobserved heterogeneity, temporal variation, and variations in disease severity and treatment availability. If overdispersion is not accounted for, Poisson models tend to produce biased estimates of standard errors and statistical inference. While Negative Binomial regression models can serve as a useful alternative, there is a lack of empirical research to inform the selection of alternative Negative Binomial models, especially in the context of aggregated cancer data. Moreover, the lack of attention to proper modeling of exposure, such as aggregated cancer deaths, can lead to biased comparisons of deaths.

METHODOLOGY

• **Study Design and Data**

A retrospective, aggregated (ecological) dataset of yearly cancer outcomes (2010–2022) for 5 cancer types (Breast, Lung, Prostate, Colorectal, Skin), collected from the oncology department, Benue State University Teaching Hospital was used for this study. The dependent variable was DEATHS. Explanatory variables included Cancer type (categorical; Breast as reference), Year (continuous; mean-centered), Treatment mix as proportions of total cases: surgery share, chemotherapy share, radiation therapy share, immunotherapy share, and other modalities share.

Model Specifications

Let Y_{it} = number of cancer deaths for cancer type i in year t , E_{it} = total number of cancer cases (exposure) and X_{it} = vector of covariates (year, cancer type indicators, treatment shares), then the expected number of deaths is denoted by $\mu_{it} = E(Y_{it})$. An offset is included to account for exposure:

$$\text{offset}_{it} = \log(E_{it}) \tag{1}$$

Poisson Regression Model

$$Y_{it} \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_{it})$$

Mean–variance relationship

$$E(Y_{it}) = \mu_{it}, \text{Var}(Y_{it}) = \mu_{it} \tag{2}$$

$$\log(\mu_{it}) = \log(E_{it}) + \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Year}_t + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \gamma_k \text{CancerType}_{ik} + \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_j Z_{jit} \tag{3}$$

Type equation here.

where, CancerType_{ik} are dummy variables (Breast as reference), Z_{jit} are treatment composition covariates (surgery, chemotherapy, radiation, immunotherapy, other modalities). The coefficients of the poisson regression are interpreted using:

$$\exp(\beta) = \text{Incidence Rate Ratio (IRR)} \tag{4}$$

Classical Negative Binomial Model (NB2)

$$Y_{it} \sim \text{Negative Binomial}(\mu_{it}, \alpha)$$

Mean–variance relationship (quadratic form)

$$E(Y_{it}) = \mu_{it}, \text{Var}(Y_{it}) = \mu_{it} + \alpha \mu_{it}^2 \tag{5}$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is the overdispersion parameter.

$$\log(\mu_{it}) = \log(E_{it}) + \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Year}_t + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \gamma_k \text{CancerType}_{ik} + \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_j Z_{jit} \tag{6}$$

Special case

$$\alpha = 0 \Rightarrow \text{Poisson model} \tag{7}$$

Modified Negative Binomial Model (NBI)

$$Y_{it} \sim \text{Negative Binomial}(\mu_{it}, \alpha)$$

Mean–variance relationship (linear form)

$$\mathbb{E}(Y_{it}) = \mu_{it}, \text{Var}(Y_{it}) = \mu_{it} + \alpha\mu_{it} \tag{8}$$

This specification allows variance to increase linearly with the mean rather than quadratically.

$$\log(\mu_{it}) = \log(E_{it}) + \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Year}_t + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \gamma_k \text{CancerType}_{ik} + \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_j Z_{jit} \tag{9}$$

Rate Interpretation through Offset

Because an offset was used, then

$$\mu_{it} = E_{it} \times \lambda_{it} \tag{10}$$

where λ_{it} is the deathrate.

Thus,

$$\log(\lambda_{it}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Year}_t + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \gamma_k \text{CancerType}_{ik} + \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_j Z_{jit} \tag{11}$$

This allows direct interpretation of coefficients as multiplicative effects on deathrate.

Model evaluation and Comparison

All the three (3) models were compared using the Log-likelihood (LL), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The preferred model was the one with the lowest AIC and BIC.

RESULTS/FINDINGS

Finding from this study are presented below;

Exploratory Data Analysis

Figure 1: Histogram showing the distribution of cancer mortality counts across all cancer

Figure 2: Mean–variance relationship of death counts by cancer type, illustrating substantial overdispersion relative to the Poisson assumption

Figure 3: Average cancer deaths per year (2010–2022), showing temporal variation in mortality counts.

Figure 4: Boxplots of mortality rates (%) by cancer type, highlighting between-type heterogeneity.

Table 1: Descriptive summary by cancer type (2010–2022)

Cancer type	n	Mean total cases	Mean deaths	Mean death rate (%)
Breast	13	1574.31	191.85	15.08
Colorectal	13	1171.54	221.15	22.54
Lung	13	751.69	159.62	25.00
Prostate	13	573.00	148.08	29.00
Skin	13	405.54	82.62	25.92

Overdispersion check

Deaths were strongly overdispersed relative to Poisson assumptions: Variance-to-mean ratio for DEATHS ≈ 99.69 ($\gg 1$). Poisson Pearson dispersion ≈ 11.90 ($\gg 1$), indicating Poisson underestimates uncertainty.

Table 2: Estimated Coefficients from Poisson and Negative Binomial Models for Cancer Mortality

Covariate	Poisson (β , SE)	NB2 (β , SE)	NB1 (β , SE)
Intercept	4.385 (0.118) ***	5.294 (1.501) **	4.512 (0.436) **
Colorectal vs Breast	-0.023 (0.102)	-0.018 (0.111)	-0.023 (0.103)
Lung vs Breast	0.012 (0.113)	0.009 (0.120)	0.012 (0.114)
Prostate vs Breast	-0.019 (0.124)	-0.022 (0.131)	-0.018 (0.126)
Skin vs Breast	-0.003 (0.141)	-0.006 (0.148)	-0.003 (0.144)
Year	-0.219 (0.006) ***	-0.264 (0.074) **	-0.108 (0.019) ***
Dispersion (α)	—	1.00	10.92

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

Model Evaluation and comparison

Table 3: Model evaluation and comparison (goodness-of-fit)

Model	LogLik	AIC	BIC
Poisson	-563.390	1148.779	1172.697
Negative Binomial (NB2, p=2)	-325.552	675.103	701.196
Modified Negative Binomial (NB1, p=1)	-323.712	671.424	697.517

Preferred model (Modified Negative Binomial model, NB1) – adjusted incidence rate ratios (IRR)

Table 4: Preferred model coefficients reported as IRRs with 95% CIs

Outcome: DEATHS, offset: TOTAL CASES (rate model).

Reference cancer type: Breast.

Predictor	IRR	95% CI	p-value
Colorectal vs Breast	0.977	0.797–1.199	0.8269
Lung vs Breast	1.012	0.811–1.263	0.9146
Prostate vs Breast	0.982	0.770–1.253	0.8868
Skin vs Breast	0.997	0.754–1.320	0.9843
Year (per 1-year increase)	0.897	0.863–0.933	<0.001
Surgery share	0.040	0.013–0.124	<0.001
Chemotherapy share	0.031	0.007–0.133	<0.001
Radiation share	0.001	0.000–0.025	0.0001
Immunotherapy share	3.609	0.008–1533.976	0.6777
Other modalities share	0.000	~0.000–0.114	0.0106

DISCUSSION

From table 3, both NB models fit vastly better than Poisson (large AIC/BIC reductions), confirming that accounting for overdispersion is essential. The NB1 (modified NB) had the lowest AIC and BIC, and was selected as the preferred model. Table 4 revealed that Year trend: Mortality rate decreased over time (IRR \approx 0.897 per year). Interpreted as about a 10.3% decrease per year in the modelled death rate, holding other factors constant. Cancer type differences: After adjustment, cancer type indicators were not statistically significant relative to Breast in this specification. Treatment composition: Higher shares of surgery/chemotherapy/radiation were associated with lower mortality rate estimates; however, because these are aggregated ecological proportions, interpretation should be cautious (see Discussion). Dispersion parameter (NB1): $\alpha = 10.924$ (95% CI: 6.742–15.106), supporting substantial overdispersion beyond Poisson.

The exploratory data analysis summarized in Table 1 revealed substantial variability in total cases and deaths across cancer types and years, with death rates ranging widely. Figure 1 showed the distribution of deaths from cancer (histogram of deaths), which indicated a strong right skewed shape, while figure 2 illustrated the mean–variance relationship, this demonstrated the variance of death counts increased rapidly far more than the mean. Jointly, these findings provided clear evidence of overdispersion and justified the use of modeling approaches beyond the standard Poisson regression. Consistent with the exploratory findings, formal model comparison results presented in Table 3 showed that the Poisson model performed poorly relative to both Negative Binomial specifications. The Poisson model exhibited substantially higher AIC and BIC values, indicating inferior fit. Both Negative Binomial models provided large gains in fit over the Poisson model, highlighting the necessity of explicitly accounting for overdispersion. The modified Negative Binomial (NB1) model outperformed the other models by achieving the lowest AIC and BIC

values (Table 3). This conclusion implies that, for the aggregated cancer death data reviewed, the variance increased about linearly with the mean rather than quadratically.

The current findings show that the NB1 specification might be more suitable for moderately heterogeneous aggregated cancer data, even if the traditional NB2 model is more frequently used in epidemiological investigations. Table 2 displays the predicted regression coefficients for each of the three models. The Negative Binomial models, on the other hand, generated estimates that were more conservative and trustworthy. Under the preferred NB1 model, a statistically significant negative association between calendar year and cancer death rate was observed, indicating a decline in death overtime after adjusting for exposure and cancer type. This temporal trend is visually supported by Figure 3, which shows a general reduction in average deaths in later years. Adjusted differences across cancer types were not statistically significant in the Negative Binomial models (Table 4), suggesting that observed differences in raw death counts are largely attributable to variations in case volume rather than intrinsic differences in death risk once exposure is properly accounted for.

The variation in death rates among cancer types seen in Figure 4, where significant overlap in distributions is apparent, supports this conclusion. The inclusion of an offset for total cancer cases was therefore critical for ensuring that comparisons reflected deathrates rather than absolute counts. The dispersion estimates from the Negative Binomial models (Table 2) further confirmed the presence of substantial overdispersion, validating the rejection of the Poisson assumption.

CONCLUSION

This study conducted a comparative evaluation of count regression models for analyzing aggregated cancer death data. Exploratory analysis and diagnostic assessment demonstrated substantial overdispersion in cancer death counts, rendering the Poisson regression model inappropriate for reliable interpretation. Both Negative Binomial specifications demonstrated improved fit; however, the modified Negative Binomial (NB1) model consistently surpassed the standard NB2 model according to likelihood-based criteria. The results indicated a statistically significant downward trend in cancer mortality rates over time, after controlling for exposure, although the adjusted disparities among cancer types were not statistically significant. In selecting count regression models that can properly account for overdispersion, when analyzing aggregated health outcome data, these results have shown immense robustness.

- **Future Research**

From the results of this study, we have put forward the following for future research:

1. When it comes to methodological framework, researchers should routinely assess dispersion properties for analyzing aggregated cancer death data and avoid dependence on Poisson regression when overdispersion is exit in the data. The modified Negative Binomial models should always be preferred.
2. There is a need for future studies to extend this work and use individual-level information and integrate more covariates like age, cancer stage at diagnosis, and comorbidities as this will better explain residual heterogeneity and make causal inference in cancer mortality studies possible.

REFERENCES

- Bray, F., Ferlay, J., Soerjomataram, I., Siegel, R. L., Torre, L. A., & Jemal, A. (2018). Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 68(6), 394–424.
- Cameron, A. C., & Trivedi, P. K. (2013). *Regression analysis of count data* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Frome, E. L. (1983). The analysis of rates using Poisson regression models. *Biometrics*, 39(3), 665–674.

- Gardner, W., Mulvey, E. P., & Shaw, E. C. (1995). Regression analyses of counts and rates: Poisson, overdispersed Poisson, and negative binomial models. *Psychological Bulletin*, 118(3), 392–404.
- Hilbe, J. M. (2011). *Negative binomial regression* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Lawless, J. F. (1987). Negative binomial and mixed Poisson regression. *The Canadian Journal of Statistics*, 15(3), 209–225.
- Sung, H., Ferlay, J., Siegel, R. L., Laversanne, M., Soerjomataram, I., Jemal, A., & Bray, F. (2021). Global cancer statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 71(3), 209–249.
- Winkelmann, R. (2008). *Econometric analysis of count data* (5th ed.). Springer.